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	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	S. Heberer, P. Gehrke	GSI	26/11/20
Edited by	P. Spiller	GSI	01/12/20
Reviewed by	M. Seidel [WP coordinator]	PSI	02/12/20
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Executive summary

Within this document the work by GSI in scope of the ARIES work package WP4 is described. The aim is to develop an energy efficient pulsed quadrupole magnet system for beam transfer lines.

In the first part improvements of an existing prototype circuit are described as well as measurements with this improved circuit.

In a second part this circuit is developed further to an energy recovery circuit which recovers part of the energy for the next pulse. Proof of principle measurements were conducted with the aim for optimization of recovered energy.

1. Introduction

As a part of the development of an energy efficiency pulsed power quadrupole system [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6], this report deals with the results of the project and also shows an outlook on further developments in the future. A comparison of the energy efficiency of magnetic transport channels for Electron- and Proton beams using different magnet technologies has been conducted [7].

The operation principle in a particle accelerator using pulsed quadrupole magnets is to apply them in beam transfer lines for bunched beams with low duty cycle ($f_{\text{rep}} < 0.5$ Hz). With a low duty cycle, the pulsed operation becomes more efficient than a conventionally DC magnet which would be fully powered without being needed most of the time. On the other side, pulsed quadrupole lenses can provide large field gradients, with an amplitude similar to superconducting magnets. With the benefit, that the required infrastructure for generating such high fields is compared to cryogenics plants and distribution system, extremely low.

An important aspect of the pulsed operation is that the current respectively the magnetic field should not change in magnitude when the beam is traveling through the magnet. For this purpose, a relatively long current pulse in the >100 μs range is generated which, depending on the length of the passing ion bunch, is only used for a small period of time (e.g. $1\mu\text{s}$) around the peak value.

Based on a Phd thesis performed at GSI, the design of a pulsed quadrupole magnet and its corresponding pulse power generator used to energize the quadrupole magnet (in the following: magnet) was further developed. The goal of this project was in a first step to improve the efficiency of the existing hardware by changing the circuit topology and in a second step to introduce an energy recovery circuit. The existing hardware and circuit at the start of this project is described in the following.

In the scope of the Phd thesis, the pulsed power generator was realized in the form of a damped RLC circuit. Figure 1 shows the sketch of this prototype circuit design to energize the magnet, Figure 2 the associated 3D-model of the real set up. The capacitor C1 is loaded by an external voltage source to a defined voltage while the switch S1 is open. If the switch closes the capacitor discharges over the magnet L1 and the damping resistor R1.

Figure 1 Damped RLC circuit

Figure 2 Simulation of the construction

The magnet and connection leads were designed for a peak current of 400 kA and a charging voltage of 23 kV. Because of hardware limitations of the other pulse circuit components, the setup was tested just up to 30 kA with a loading voltage of 4.5 kV. The low value of the current results from the high resistance of 100 mΩ, which was needed to prevent oscillation. Nevertheless, the first step was made to utilize a low duty cycle for a better efficiency with a pulsed magnet. To increase the peak current for a given loading voltage respectively to increase the efficiency further, an improved circuit was realized.

2. Improved circuit

Figure 3 shows the circuit diagram of the improved circuit. In this circuit the current is increased due to the removal of the resistor in the main current path through the magnet. In order to still prevent the circuit from oscillation a diode D1 was connected parallel to block the positive and conduct the negative half wave of the current. A picture of the whole setup can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Circuit diagram of the improved circuit

Also, the resistor R1 shown in Figure 1 has been removed. Due to the current limitations of the diode a resistance is still needed to protect the diode. This was realized with the new resistor R2 that can be chosen with a value ten times lower than R1. In turn, the lower resistance value and the fact that it is connected in parallel leads to a higher current magnitude.

More precise, the current through the magnet in this set-up increases by approximately 150 % compared to the prototype circuit at the same charging voltage. **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 4 Improved circuit

shows the simulation at 1 kV for the improved circuit. Figure 6 shows the simulation for the prototype circuit at 1 kV loading voltage. The current increases from approx. 7 kA to 18 kA or in other words the loading voltage/energy can be reduced significantly in the improved circuit for a desired current magnitude. The realistic quantity of this efficiency improvement is investigated within measurements in the next chapter.

Figure 5 Simulation at 1 kV loading voltage with improved circuit

Figure 6 Simulation at 1 kV loading voltage with prototype circuit

2.1 MEASUREMENTS WITH IMPROVED CIRCUIT

Measurements with this setup were made up to 3.5 kV loading voltage. This value was not exceeded due to the limiting components in the circuit. The diode is specified for a maximum forward surge

current of 52 kA. To limit the peak current to 40 - 45 kA for safety reasons, the upper limit of the loading voltage was set to 3.5 kV. Furthermore, another hardware restriction is the maximum loading voltage of the capacitor of 5 kV.

Figure 7 shows the measurements at the maximum loading voltage for this setup. The current through the magnet was measured with a Rogowski coil (Powertek type: CWT 300R).

The oscillation after the peak current are caused by leakage inductances in the circuit. The current has its peak value at approximately 47 kA for a loading voltage of 3.5 kV. The peak current is lower than the simulation used in chapter 2 is predicting for this loading voltage (simulations: 63 kA at 3.5 kV). This difference is expectable as only arbitrary small parasitic resistances were included in this simulation.

With approx. 20 mΩ additional resistance in the main circuit the peak current in the simulation and measurement matches. This is a reasonable value taking into account that this includes the parasitic

Figure 7 Measurement at 3.5 kV with improved circuit

resistances of the magnet, capacitor, switch, and the whole current leads of the main circuit. Nevertheless, the measurements have shown that the energy needed for one pulse is reduced significantly by 80% in the improved circuit (e.g. from 12.6kJ to 2.7kJ for one 50kA pulse). This already reduced energy demand will be decreased further by an energy recovery circuit in the next chapter.

3. Energy recovery

In order to set up an energy recovery circuit that recovers a part of the capacitors initial energy the parallel circuit was rebuilt. Figure 8 shows the basic structure with a recovery circuit. Compared to the previous circuit (Figure 3) a diode (D1) was connected in series with the quadrupole magnet in the main circuit. It conducts the positive pulse through the quadrupole magnet and blocks a negative oscillation in this part of the circuit. The diode (D2) in the recovery circuit does the exact opposite in form of blocking the positive pulse and let through the negative. They are essential to prevent the circuit from oscillation and avoid a ringing discharge. In addition, the damping resistor (R2) of the improved circuit has been removed because the current is limited by the large dummy inductance and its parasitic resistance. With this circuit the advantages of the improved circuit are kept while implementing an additional energy recovery.

Figure 8 Energy recovery circuit

The dummy inductance is required to temporary store the energy of the negative pulse. The type and value of the dummy inductance and the corresponding copper losses are an optimization criterion in this setup. On the one hand increasing the inductance affects, without any core material, the copper resistance of the coil due to the winding length. The copper resistance is responsible for the thermal losses which affect the recovered energy. On the other hand, a bigger inductance leads to a longer pulse but with a lower magnitude. As an example, Figure 9 shows the current through the dummy inductance for different inductivities ($100 \mu H$ to $1 mH$; step width $100 \mu H$). The blue graph shows the current at $100 \mu H$ and the brown on at $1 mH$.

Figure 9 Simulation of currents through dummy inductivity for different dummy inductances values

For a better assessment of the circuit behaviour Figure 10 shows results of a simulation for the recovered voltage as a function of different dummy inductances and resistances. It can be seen, that starting from the minimum it is a factor of 1/10 in resistance to reach the area >700 V recovered

Figure 10 Recovered voltage for different dummy inductances and coil resistances

voltage but a factor 90 in inductance. This leads to the assumption that it is more convenient to keep the coil resistance low.

Figure 11 Energy recovery construction with air-core coil

For the first proof of principle and to check the assumptions, an air-core coil was wound and subsequently used as the dummy inductance. For this purpose, a flat copper strip with a width of 5 mm was wrapped with 220 turns around a PVC pipe with a diameter of 165 mm and a length of about 1.2 m (Figure 11). Based on the formula $L = \mu_0 \mu_r \frac{A \cdot N^2}{l}$ it follows an inductance of

approximately 1 mH. The resulting conductor resistance value of the copper strip based on the formula $R = \rho \frac{l}{A}$ is at nearly 0.3 Ω.

3.1 MEASUREMENTS WITH THE ENERGY RECOVERY CIRCUIT

The measurement in the following Figure 12 shows the current through the dummy and the voltage at the capacitor. With a loading voltage of approximately 1 kV, the input energy is at 225 J. The peak current at this voltage is roughly at 0.4 kA. A voltage of approximately 525 V was recovered. This corresponds to a recovered energy of 62 J. Therefore, nearly 28 % of the used energy is available to be used for a following pulse.

Figure 12 Measurement of dummy current and capacitor voltage

In order to confirm the considerations in chapter 3 about the dependence of the recovered voltage on inductance and resistance the dummy coil was halved. For this purpose, a connection at the middle of the coil was soldered onto the winding and connected to the circuit. Thereby, the inductance was one quarter and the resistance was halved. The measurements in Figure 13 show that the current through the main circuit increases and the current pulse width decreases as expected. However, the recovered voltage is almost unchanged. This behaviour leads to the conclusion that change in inductance cancel out the lower resistance and therefore simply changing this coil by removing or adding turns is not advantageous and will not result in an optimum. Still, it was shown that even with a rather simple and not yet optimized dummy inductance 28% of the energy could be recovered.

Figure 13 Measurement 1 kV half coil

Conclusions & future plans

In the scope of this work, an existing prototype setup of a pulsed quadrupole magnet was improved regarding its energy efficiency. In the first part, it was shown that by changing the circuit topology therefore making a high damping resistance unnecessary, the energy per shot can be reduced significantly. Measurements with this improved circuit were done to verify this solution and to adapt the components in the simulation for more realistic behaviour.

In the second part, the improved circuit was converted in an energy recovery circuit which recovers part of the energy for the next pulse. The dimensioning of the energy recovery coil regarding inductance and resistance values was discussed. Proof of principle measurements were conducted with approx. 28% energy recovery. In combination with the 80% increase in efficiency of the improved circuit, this is a substantial step in relation to the project start. Furthermore, the dimensioning of the energy recovery coil was investigated within the measurements. The results show that no optimum can be found with the simple coil configuration used in this setup, but a design goal for the future was worked out.

For future work, a design goal should be to reduce the resistance for a given inductance by another winding technique with the aim of reducing the needed conductor length as well as optimizing the used conductor cross section. Another design goal should be to increase the inductance significantly, while keeping a certain coil resistance, e.g. by using a ferromagnetic material for the core of the coil. It has to be elaborated which option is the more promising to start with.

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